

Sorption Behaviour of Some Amino Acids on Chemically Pretreated Alumina

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Chemical pretreatment of hydrous oxides resulting in the evokement of ion-exchangeable sites has been advocated. To investigate the deeper aspects of the concept, alumina samples of surface pH 3.5-8.5 were prepared by treating Brockmann alumina with varying concentrations of hydrochloric and nitric acid. Sorption behaviour of an amino acid (glutamic acid) on these substrates under varying concentrations, time, temperature and desorbents was investigated. The process is found to be pH-dependent and the favourable range is pH 3.0-5.0. The greater degree of sorption in short time interval (10 min), its athermic nature (30-60°) and easy desorption with inorganic anions ($\text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{Cl}^- / \text{NO}_3^-$) have been interpreted by a predominant ion-exchange mechanism.

AMINO acids are ampholytes and at neutral pH in aq. solution they exist as polar species. Change of pH beyond their isoelectric point has a significant effect on the net charge. This, in turn, can play an important role in their sorption behaviour on polar sorbents. Some empirical studies¹ have shown the significance of pH in the sorption of amino acids on alumina. However, the nature of specific interactions and the type of surface sites responsible for the interaction is still not clear. Hence glutamic acid was taken up to investigate (i) change in the nature of sorption of the amino acid on alumina pretreated with mineral acids to obtain substrates of varying pH (1.0-8.5), and (ii) desorption behaviour of the amino acid with aq. solutions of inorganic electrolytes ($\text{NaCl}/\text{NaNO}_3$, Na_2SO_4 , Na_3PO_4 , etc.).

Experimental

HCl treated alumina samples of surface pH 3.5-8.5 were prepared as described earlier². Following the same general method, nitric acid treated samples of pH 3.5-8.5 were also prepared. In the present work surface pH of the alumina samples means surface phase pH, and pH of 1% aq. extract of the sample has been taken as surface pH or surface phase pH. The conditions are reproduced in Tables 1A and 1B. Anion exchange capacity of the alumina samples was determined by pH-metric titration method and was found to be in the range of 0.48-0.19 meq. g⁻¹ for HCl-treated Al_2O_3 (pH 3.5-7.0) and 0.12-0.01 meq. g⁻¹ for HNO_3 -treated Al_2O_3 (pH 3.5-7.0).

Glutamic acid (B.D.H.) was dried at 105° and stored over drierite. All other chemicals were of

TABLE 1A—PREPARATION OF HNO_3 -TREATED ALUMINA OF VARYING pH

pH of alumina prepared	Normality of the acid used (N)	Period of contact during shaking (min)	pH of the wash liquid	pH of the washed alumina after initial drying
8.5	0.0100	50	8.6	8.5
8.0	0.0125	50	8.4	8.2
7.5	0.0150	20	8.0	7.7
7.0	0.0150	50	7.5	7.1
6.5	0.0175	20	7.2	6.6
6.0	0.0175	50	6.8	6.1
5.5	0.0200	50	6.0	5.6
5.0	0.0250	50	5.5	5.1
4.8	0.0400	50	5.2	4.9
4.5	0.0500	50	5.0	4.6
4.0	0.0750	50	4.5	4.1
3.5	0.1000	50	4.0	3.6

TABLE 1B—PREPARATION OF HNO_3 -TREATED ALUMINA OF pH < 3.5

pH of alumina prepared	pH of the alumina initially taken : 3.5 (0.10 g in 10 ml)	
	Normality (N)	Volume (ml)
3.0	0.01	1.0
2.5	0.10	0.4
2.0	0.10	1.0

A.R. grade. From the stock solution of glutamic acid in water ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), 5-80 ml solutions were withdrawn, diluted to 100 ml, and estimated colorimetrically at 570 nm, using ninhydrin as colorimetric reagent³. "Spekol" spectrophotometer (Carl-Zeiss) was used for the purpose.

Sorption experiments were conducted by equilibrating alumina (0.10 g) with aq. amino acid solutions of known concentration in 10 ml volumetric

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flasks. The flasks were immersed in thermostat at desired temperature and periodically shaken. After a specified period, 2 ml aliquot withdrawn, centrifuged and estimated.

Sorption vs time and temperature :

The variation of sorption as a function of time (10 min-6 hr) was studied with the samples of pH 2.0-8.0 at 30°. Glutamic acid shows fast sorption on both the type of samples and 65-75% sorption occurs only in 10 min. However, the equilibrium reaches in 4 hr. The temperature effect studies (30-60°, 4 hr, pH 2.0-8.0) show the process to be almost athermic.

Sorption vs pH :

The results are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. The phenomenon is found to be pH-dependent. It increases in the pH range 2.0-3.5 and then decreases in the range of pH 4.5-8.5. Maximum sorption occurs at pH 3.5. The sorption is found to be concentration-dependent. The isotherms are of L-type not having a well-defined plateau (especially at $pH < 4.5$) probably because of the low amino acid concentrations.

Reversibility of sorption :

The study was made in two ways :

- (i) Keeping the inorganic electrolytes in the sorption bath with the amino acid substrates, and
- (ii) Washing the sorbed species with the desorbents.

For this purpose, sorption studies were made using the solute and the electrolytes ($\text{NaCl}/\text{NaNO}_3$, Na_2SO_4 , Na_2PO_4) of the same concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$).

Fig. 1. Change in the nature of asorption of glutamic acid from aqueous solutions on HCl-treated alumina of varying pH.

(Time : 6 hr ; Temp. 30°)

Fig. 2. Change in the nature of asorption of glutamic acid from aqueous solutions on HNO_3 -treated alumina of varying pH.

(Time : 6 hr ; Temp. 30°)

Fig. 3. Change in percentage asorption of glutamic acid with varying pH of acid-treated alumina.

(6 hr, 30°, $[\text{Glutamic acid}]_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ moles/litre).

Alumina used in the studies was of pH 2.0-8.0. It is observed that sorption decreases significantly and retarding influence is in the order $\text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$.

Desorption of the amino acid sorbed (pH 4.0-8.0, 30°, 6 hr) was attempted with aq. inorganic electrolytes (0.1-0.001 M, $\text{NaCl}/\text{NaNO}_3$, CH_3COONa , Na_2SO_4 , $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ or Na_2PO_4). The solute solu-

tion (250 ml, 1.0×10^{-3} and 2.0×10^{-4} M) was equilibrated with the sorbent (2.5 g), the supernatant liquid decanted, centrifuged and estimated. The solid phase was washed repeatedly with water till the washings were free from the amino acid (ninhydrin test). The washed sample containing sorbed solute was dried (80° , 12 hr), and stored.

The alumina loaded with the solute (0.10 g) was shaken with aq. electrolytes in 10 ml volumetric flasks. The flasks were immersed in thermostat at 30° , and periodically shaken. After 2 hr, 2.0 ml of aliquot withdrawn, centrifuged and estimated.

The studies reveal that PO_4^{3-} ions (0.1 M–0.01 M) desorb the amino acid quantitatively. The desorption efficacy is in the order $\text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- > \text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$. It is also observed that desorption gradually increases with increase in the pH of alumina and concentration of the electrolyte.

Results and Discussion

The anion-exchange property of alumina pretreated with HCl or HNO_3 has long been observed^{1,4,5} and postulated as under :

The anions present on the surface may either be covalently bound or present as hydrated ions, depending upon the nature of the anions.

Fuller⁶ attributes the apparent ion-exchange capacity of alumina to the amphoteric reaction of hydroxyl groups contained in the structure of alumina as shown below :

The upper reactions, producing anion-exchange properties, are favoured at low pH, whereas the lower reactions result in cation-exchange characteristics. The results in favour of the ion exchange nature of the process are (i) athermic nature of the process and significant quick sorption, (ii) reversibility of sorption and salt effect. In presence of the electrolytes, sorption is retarded considerably and it appears that the anions having greater affinity for the surface are being retarded. Potentiometric

studies of Cl^- ions and spectrophotometric estimation of the NO_3^- ions released after sorption, also show an increase in the concentration of the ions at $\text{pH} \leq 5.0$.

pH and sorption : Glutamic acid is a mono-amino dicarboxylic acid with $\text{pK}_1 = 2.19$, $\text{pK}_2 = 4.25$ ($-\text{COOH}$), $\text{pK}_3 = 9.67$ ($-\text{NH}_3^+$) at 25° . The isoelectric point (pI) is $\text{pH} 3.32$. Hence at $\text{pH} \geq 3.5$, it will be essentially in the anionic form $[-\text{OOC}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}(\text{NH}_3^+)\text{COO}^-]$. The optimum pH of sorption observed is also $\text{pH} 3.5$. At $\text{pH} < 3.5$, concentration of the chloride/nitrate ions on the substrate surface and in solution increases, and the ionic species responsible for sorption decreases. The behaviour is so prominent that the amino acid shows about 40% sorption at $\text{pH} 2.0$. At $\text{pH} > 3.5$ the proportion of exchangeable chloride/nitrate decreases, and hence the sorption goes on decreasing significantly upto $\text{pH} 6.0$. At $\text{pH} > 6.0$, however, the sorption decreases gradually and hardly 8% of the solute is sorbed at $\text{pH} 8.5$. The above change in the sorption behaviour of the acid may be due to change in the nature of species. We know that the pK_2 and pK_3 values of the amino acid are 4.25 ($-\text{COOH}$) and 9.67 ($-\text{NH}_3^+$), respectively. Rapid exchange of the solute anions appears to occur at $\text{pH} < 6.0$ followed by a slow exchange. It has been observed that in the pH range 3.0–6.0, the rate of $\text{Cl}^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ -amino acid-anion exchange is proportional to the concentration of the ingoing ions, indicating slow film diffusion. Further, affinity of the solute for the substrate in the alkaline pH range may be due to hydrogen bonding with the surface oxygen atoms of alumina. The L-type isotherms indicate monolayer sorption.

Degree of sorption vs the acid used for treatment :

In the ion-selectivity series of oxides/hydrrous oxides, both Cl^- and NO_3^- are much below the OH^- ions. However, the Cl^- ion is just above the NO_3^- ion. Hence, it is expected that the treatment of alumina with either HCl or HNO_3 should result in an ion-exchanger. This is also revealed by the pH vs percentage sorption data (Fig. 3). Sorption of the solute on $\text{HNO}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is higher than that of $\text{HCl} - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ in the pH range 2.0 to 4.5.

Conclusion :

Thus, it appears that the sorptive forces involved in the adsorption of glutamic acid on HCl and HNO_3 treated alumina are predominantly coulombic (ion-exchange), and the affinity of the amino acid is strongly dependent on pH of the substrate. The behaviour has been suitably applied for chromatographic separation of amino acids (to be communicated).

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References

1. E. LEDERER and M. LEDERER, "Chromatography", Elsevier Publishing Co., 2nd Edn., 1967, p. 291.
2. G. L. MUNDHARA and J. S. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 1033.
3. F. D. SNELL and C. T. SNELL, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis", Van Nostrand Co., 1967, Vol. IV A, p. 216.
4. D. J. O'CONNOR, A. S. BUCHANAN and P. G. JOHNSON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **50**, 229.
5. G. L. MUNDHARA, J. S. TIWARI, and M. P. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 798 ; 1980, **57**, 404.
6. M. J. FULLER, *Chromatogr. Review*, 1971, **14**, 45.